

‘You just have to build the bridge’: An interview study on the influence of socially assistive robots on professional-client relationships

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1 Background

Care and nursing are commonly associated with ‘tender love’, a deeply human and emotional practice that is often contrasted with the perceived rationality and coldness of technology^[1]. Despite this dichotomy, technology has always played an important role in healthcare, facilitating medical interventions, monitoring patients, and improving the efficiency of care^[2, 3, 4]. However, the introduction of robotic technology raises new ethical and philosophical questions about the relationship between care and technology within human interaction. This is particularly relevant in elderly care, where socially assistive robots (SARs) are designed to provide not only practical assistance, but also companionship and emotional interaction.

SARs are embodied tools aimed at assisting older adults through companionship and daily activity support^[5, 6]. Their design often incorporates anthropomorphic or zoomorphic features to increase user acceptance^[7]. The increasing presence of SARs in elderly care has sparked intense debate as it challenges conventional notions of ‘good care’. The International Council of Nurses’^[8] Code of Ethics states that nursing is inextricably linked to respect for human rights, dignity and autonomy. Likewise, according to the German Ethics Council^[9], nursing is essentially interpersonal and cannot be fully replaced by technology. This ethical foundation raises important questions about the potential impact of SARs on care: How do SARs influence the professional-client relationship and the professional self-understanding of professional caregivers?

Coeckelbergh^[2] identifies ten aspects of ‘good care’ and links them to two philosophical traditions: (1) care ethics, as formulated by Fisher and Tronto^[10], and (2) phenomenological-hermeneutic approaches. Two key aspects of ‘good care’ are particularly relevant when assessing SARs in elderly care: first, care inherently includes psychological and relational dimensions, such as emotional support; second, ‘good care’ requires skilled engagement that goes beyond formal expertise to include practical know-how and caregiving craftsmanship^[2]. This distinguishes the integration of robots in care from other domains, such as industry or transportation, where efficiency and automation are paramount^[11]. Caring for the elderly involves work for, with, and on people, with an emphasis on emotional connection and comfort that cannot be fully reconciled with the logic of technological efficiency^[12, 13]. Because of this perceived tension between the essence of care and the use of machines, the introduction of SARs in elderly care has sparked extensive ethical

and philosophical debates^[2, 14, 15, 16]. Much of the discussion revolves around concerns about the reduction of human contact in robotic care, a critique that is particularly pronounced in contexts involving vulnerable individuals such as the elderly^[17, 18, 19].

Vandemeulebroucke et al.^[15] identify two dominant perspectives in these debates: First, the ‘care-romantic’ perspective argues that SARs dehumanize eldercare, objectify elders, and promote a dystopian future where technology replaces human interaction^[17, 19, 20, 21]. Rooted in the belief that caring is a natural, deeply human activity, this view holds that machines can never meaningfully replicate care^[19, 21]. However, this view tends to overlook the already deeply technological nature of modern elderly care and risks falling to a naturalistic fallacy, equating the natural with the morally good. It can lead to overly restrictive and unjustified policies. Second is the ‘techno-deterministic’ perspective, which argues that SARs provide necessary solutions to current and future challenges in elderly care, such as workforce shortages and rising care demands^[22, 23, 24]. This perspective assumes that SARs represent an inevitable stage of technological development and presupposes a structural need for their implementation in the elderly care sector^[20, 22, 23, 25, 26]. Yet, it risks legitimizing overly permissive guidelines that fail to reflect the complexity of care relationships. Empirical studies highlight the ambivalence of these technologies: while they may improve the identification of care needs and reduce physical strain, they may also introduce new complexities and burdens for caregivers^[27]. We argue that these studies point to a third stance towards technology in elderly care^[3] which, as Verbeek^[28] has outlined, focuses on how technologies help to shape actions, decisions and practices, while reflecting on the ethical implications.

Where SARs are introduced in care contexts, their implementation will be shaped by care recipients, but also by (professional) caregivers, who will decide how and whether to use them, depending on what the technology offers. It is therefore critical to include perspectives of relevant stakeholders in these negotiations, and to attend closely to specific technological artefacts to better understand and debate their ethical and practical implications. Traditionally, caregiving has been conceptualized as a dyadic interaction between caregiver and care recipient. However, the introduction of SARs become part of the care process, therefore changing this relationship. This shift requires a rethinking of roles, responsibilities and professional self-understanding in care^[29]. Consequently, it is crucial to facilitate interpretive dialogue with stakeholders^[6] and encourage the active involvement of caregivers in these discussions^[30].

Therefore, our study explores the impact of SARs on caring relationships and professional self-perception from the perspective of caregivers in inpatient elderly care. We analyze how professional caregivers perceive the introduction of SARs, how they conceptualize their own roles and those of the SARs in their caring relationships, and how they establish ethical boundaries around the use of such technologies. Our findings reveal a transition from a dyadic to a triadic model of care. It is important to understand this shift, as it reveals how care practices and professional self-perception evolve alongside technology. This provides valuable insights into the ethical implementation of SARs and our understanding of ‘good care’.

2 Research design

To develop a model of how care interactions might change with SAR use, a constructivist grounded theory approach^[31] was chosen. Twelve semi-structured interviews^[32] were conducted with care professionals with experience employing SARs in Germany. Four interviews with other stakeholders were included to cover multiple perspectives. The interview study is part of the mixed-methods project ‘Ethics Guidelines for Socially Assistive Robots in Elderly Care: An Empirical-Participatory Approach (E-cARE)’, which includes a literature review, a citizens’ conference,^[33] and ethics guidelines for using SARs. The COREQ criteria were used to guide the writing of this section^[34].

2.1 Participant selection and recruitment

The sampling strategy was purposive. We were interested in the perspectives of those employing SARs in inpatient elderly care. This group included (geriatric) nurses and care assistants who organize social interactions. We aimed for maximum variation of perspectives in terms of work setting, work experiences, time spent working with robots and type of robots used. Institutions using SARs were identified through web searches. Snowball sampling was also used.

Participants were contacted by email and telephone to arrange an interview. Before the interview, the participant received an email containing study information, an informed consent form and a short socio-demographic questionnaire. 16 Interviews were conducted with 18 participants, as one interview involved three people from different organizational levels.

To understand how SARs are used today (and in line with a grounded theory approach), we included four people who were not directly involved in care, but shape SAR integration. Specifically, they were from the fields of applied science, technical support, management and caregiver training. In the German context, it is important to note that SARs remain largely piloted and are mostly conducted in funded (research) projects. Requests to participate were declined for a variety of reasons (twelve institutions), including lack of personnel resources, high interest but commitments to other studies (and media engagements), or because SARs were no longer in use due to practical barriers (e.g. unstable Wi-Fi), the conclusion of a funded project, or lack of technical support.

2.2 Data collection

The interview guide (see appendix) was developed using the process established by Helfferich^[32] and discussed in a workshop with other qualitative researchers for validation. Due to the small number of interviewees available, it was not pre-tested but continually adapted. CK (4 interviews) and MB (12 interviews) conducted the interviews. Interviews were audio-recorded using a voice recorder and lasted between 25 and 90 minutes. They were then transcribed, and all personal or identifiable information was pseudonymized. Initial notes and thoughts were collected during the interviews, followed by the production of a postscript.

2.3 Data analysis

Data analysis followed a constructivist grounded theory approach^[31]. Inductive coding was the first stage of analysis: The data was read and reread and then analyzed to identify units of meaning. Conceptual labels (codes) were used to divide the data (into words, phrases or lines). Codes that related to or represented similar concepts in respondents' experiences were combined into groups. The categories and the overall analytical framework were developed using codes. To deepen the analysis, the data were condensed in a second round to extract and refine the main categories and to highlight their relationship (focused coding). In addition, theoretical coding was used to bring the findings into conversation with existing concepts in nursing theory and ethics, such as the supposed antithesis of technology and the human touch and 'good care'. Data were coded by MB, CVK and CK. In joint coding groups codes were compared and relationships between categories were mapped (MB, CK, MB, CVK). In addition, categories were presented in interpretation groups (e.g. with nurses) and team meetings. MAXQDA24 was used to code the data.

2.4 Setting

The interviews were conducted in Germany between April 2023 and April 2024. Five interviews were conducted in person at the institutions, seven by video call and four by telephone. The interviewees mostly preferred the latter two formats, as they were less time-consuming. To get a feel for care setting, both interviewers conducted at least one interview at the interviewee's workplace. One interview was conducted with three people as this provided the perspectives of the institution, the local caregiver and the supporting academic institution.

2.5 Sample Characteristics

The participating institutions were located across Germany and varied in type, from open day centers to closed institutions that specialized in dementia care. The sample includes six trained nurses, three allied health professionals and nine others (e.g. educational scientist, public health scientist, technical support) (see Table 1). There were 14 women and four men in the sample, aged between 26 and 64, with care experience ranging from three to 40 years, and experience with the SARs ranging from first approaches (a few days ago) to eight years. The robotic systems used by participants included Lio (2x), Navel (2x), Paro (3x), Pepper (7x), JAIme (2x) and YANNY (2x). As some facilities employ more than one system, the total number of systems is higher than the number of interviews conducted.

Table 1 Information about the sample

No.	Position / Role ^a	Robotic system used	Experience ^b	Interview type
1	Care assistant (‘Betreuungskraft’)	Paro	intermediate	alone
2	Care assistant (‘Betreuungskraft’)	Paro	intermediate	alone
3	Social education worker (organizational development)	Paro	senior	alone
4	Public health scientist (project coordination)	Pepper	junior	alone
5	Health Care Support Worker (‘Heilerziehungskraft’)	Pepper JAIime YANNY	junior	alone
6	Nurse (Nursing home management)	Pepper JAIime YANNY	senior	alone
7	Social education worker (Social assistant)	Pepper	junior	jointly
8	Nurse (Organizational development)	Pepper	senior	jointly
9	Researcher (Socio robotics)	Pepper	-	jointly
10	Geriatric Nurse (Nursing home management)	Pepper	senior	alone
11	Nurse	Navel	senior	alone
12	Leadership (Organizational development)	Navel	junior	alone
13	(Palliative) Nurse (Nursing home management)	Lio	senior	alone
14	Nurse	Lio	junior	alone
Additional Interviews				
15	Organizational development (Technical Support)	-	-	alone
16	Researcher (Social informatics)	-	-	alone
17	User experience specialist (Robot implementation)	-	-	alone
18	Social education worker (Professional education)	-	-	alone

^a In order to maintain pseudonymisation, the pseudonyms of the interview partners have not been included here due to the relatively small field.

^b junior (<5 years), intermediate (between >5 and <10 years), and senior (>10 years).

2.6 Reflexivity

Data collection and analysis was mainly undertaken by CK and MB. CK was the co-project lead and is an interdisciplinary health scientist with a focus on empirical bioethics. MB worked as a researcher on the project and is a trained sociologist with a focus on qualitative methods. Both researchers had previous experience of conducting qualitative research, particularly semi-structured interviews with health professionals. In addition, CVK, a research assistant trained in life sciences, coded all the interviews. The project and parts of the analysis were discussed in internal team meetings, colloquiums and an interdisciplinary interpretation group that included nurses and physicians. Their practical insights greatly enriched the interpretations.

2.7 Ethical considerations

The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Potsdam (No. 84/2022). Written informed consent was obtained from each participant prior to inclusion in the study. Data were pseudonymized and original audio recordings deleted after transcription to protect participants.

3 Results

The findings highlight the complex transition caregivers experience when integrating SARs. This shift is marked by a transformation from a dyadic (human-to-human) to a triadic (human-robot-human) care relationship model. The integration process unfolds in three distinct phases, each representing a key stage in this transformation. They are temporally ordered and reflect a progression in caregivers’ practical and normative engagement with SARs over time:

- [1] Initial Phase: Characterized by dyadic resistance and skepticism toward SARs.
- [2] Usage phase: Involves the recalibration of relational model as SARs are incorporated into daily care practices.
- [3] Reflexive phase: Entail the reconfiguration of triadic relationships as caregivers adapt and develop normative frameworks.

3.1 Initial Phase: Fears of displacing the human element of care

Initially, caregivers expressed concern about SAR implementation, which they perceived as a potential threat to relational care. This resistance is rooted in a dyadic model of caregiving, in which the caregiver-client relationship is seen as fundamental to providing ‘good care’. From the caregivers’ perspective, both they and care recipients alike expressed concern about the erosion of the human connection. A recurring theme in the interviews was the fear that SARs could replace human caregivers, undermining interpersonal relationships:

“Sure, the question always comes up in the second sentence: ‘Are they going to replace us living people?’ And we always answer: ‘We hope not.’ (...) Because of course the biggest fear of the seniors is that the human connection will disappear altogether.” (Mehl)¹

Underlying such concern is the conceptualization of the SAR as a potential new partner in a dyadic relationship. Such a development is feared, as it implies substituting the human element with a robotic one. Furthermore, concerns were raised about the economic motivations behind the implementation. Caregivers feared that SARs would be used as a cost-saving measure, prioritizing efficiency over quality of care:

“I’m worried about robots being misused - residents being left with robots just because it’s cheaper. That would be a nightmare. Care is about human warmth, about seeing what someone needs in the moment. A robot can’t do that, no matter how many sensors or cameras it has.” (Stein)

Their relational understanding is contradicted by this supposed economic rationale. They believe that maintaining care as relational work with a ‘human connection’ is a normative obligation that ethical institutions must address:

“I’m just afraid that more and more people will say, ‘Yeah, we’ve got a robot here. So we don’t need a human.’ And that is a political decision (...). That’s why I think it’s really a matter for the German Ethics Council (...) that care remains human. (...) As I said, I’m a fan of all this, but as an addition and not as a replacement.” (Nau)

In addition, caregivers were skeptical about the ability of SARs to authentically emulate emotional and social behaviors. They feared that artificial emotional engagement could create misleading or inauthentic connections with care recipients, ultimately damaging trust. In summary, caregivers were skeptical in the early stages of SAR implementation. While they recognized the potentials of SARs, they emphasized the irreplaceability of human empathy, warmth, and judgment in caregiving. Their reservation was rooted in a dyadic model of care, which views the relationship as fundamental for the notion of ‘good care’. Implementing SARs therefore runs the risk of replacing human caregivers with robotic ones. However, as the next phase shows, this view begins to shift with practical experience in working alongside SARs.

3.2 Usage Phase: Integrating SARs and recalibrating the relationship model

In retrospect, the professionals described how their initial expectations changed as they began to work with SARs. They observed that SARs had limited autonomy, could not fully engage with

¹All names in this article are pseudonyms. Translations by MB and CK.

care recipients, and required constant supervision. This realization led to a recalibration of the relationship model: instead of replacing caregivers, SARs became part of a collaborative triad in which their effectiveness depended on caregivers’ ability to adapt and integrate them into daily practices:

“At first, we thought that if we just put Pepper in the room, something might happen. But we learned that if you just put the robot in the dining room, it will be ignored. It just doesn’t work that way. As a person, you really must build a bridge to the elderly.” (Pieper)

With understanding the limited functionality of SARs, professionals had to adapt their conceptualization of SARs as a replacement technology. Instead, they were reinterpreted as a tool to support certain care tasks that are then carried out by a triad constellation, perhaps more effectively than a dyad could do. For example, where robotic technology is available, the task of calming down an agitated dementia patient can be realized by three entities working together: the care recipient interacting with a robotic seal Paro and the care professional who facilitates this interaction:

“The seal can calm down. (...) The care recipients can stroke and can practically get rid of everything they have inside them for a moment. Then the facial expression relaxes, the body relaxes.” (Nau)

Interestingly, SARs are most often used to assist with specific routine tasks, freeing nurses to focus on the relational aspects of care:

“It’s important that robots don’t replace staff. Robots should only support us, like reading recipes to seniors who want to cook, while I provide one-on-one care to someone who really needs it.” (Dorn)

This perspective highlights the role of SARs in performing logistical or repetitive tasks, such as organizing schedules or facilitating group activities. It reinforces the idea that human professionals are responsible for the relational and emotional aspects of care. In this triadic model, caregivers maintained their relationships with care recipients because they facilitated interactions with SARs. Their role ensured that SARs were perceived as a tool to enhance, rather than replace, human connection:

“Caring is about human warmth, empathy and understanding what someone needs in the moment. A robot, no matter how advanced, can’t do that.” (Stein)

While SARs are mostly conceptualized as tools, it is still a relationship that is formed as the following statement illustrates:

“In the beginning we also had to deal with some prejudice: now Pepper comes and replaces the caregivers. No, he doesn’t. He is an addition. But now he really is an integral part, and somehow, he belongs. Well, that had to develop. It wasn’t like that from the beginning.” (Pieper)

Unlike traditional care objects (books or memory games) SARs were perceived as social agents capable of eliciting attachment. As such, their integration into care facilities required intentional effort from staff to foster a sense of familiarity and connection among both caregivers and residents. For example, in one case, the SAR was introduced as a “new trainee” and then gradually became part of the team: “But now he’s just part of the team and that’s a good thing” (Erich). Care recipients formed bonds with the SARs, often treating them more like companions than tools:

“The seniors like to shake his hand, just say hello and then he says something. (...) The dementia patients react very positively to this and then talk to him or are simply happy that he looks cute and comes.” (Pieper)

While initial concerns focused on job displacement which could be dissolved by experience, these fears often gave way to disappointment with the SARs’ functional limitations. Many caregivers found it frustrating that SARs lacked autonomy and required constant human intervention to perform effectively. For example, they needed to manage technical issues, such as software errors. One participant contrasted the limited capabilities of SARs with inexpensive consumer technologies:

“The need for constant supervision was a recurring theme. (...) With Pepper, there always must be someone with him – a caregiver or a housekeeper – to do something with him. It’s a bit of a disappointment, because you’d expect it to be able to do more, you know? When I think about Alexa at home, it costs 30 euros, and you can almost have a conversation with it. With Pepper you can’t.” (Kaya)

This comparison between low-cost consumer technology and the expensiveness of SARs fueled skepticism about whether robotics in their current state could meaningfully reduce workload or improve quality of care. This shows how caregivers, through their SAR experiences, gradually adjust their relationship model from a dyadic to a triadic structure. In this reconfigured model, they continue to see themselves as key mediators in establishing and managing this triadic relationship between care recipients, SARs and themselves. Based on their experiences, they reflect on their professional moral obligation in SAR use – although, due to their disappointment with the current development level of SARs, much of this reflection was on possible future developments.

3.3 Reflective Phase: Establishing normative boundaries for SAR use

Caregivers consistently emphasized the need to establish ethical boundaries for the SAR use. Their perspectives reflect a strong commitment to ensuring that technology serves as a supportive tool, not a replacement, and preserves the human-centered values that define their profession. As mentioned in the first phase, the fundamental principle articulated by caregivers was that SARs should augment, but never replace, human caregiving. This belief shaped how caregivers integrated and used SARs. SARs were often seen most appropriate for logistical and repetitive tasks, such as distributing finger food or encouraging people to drink. When used for social tasks, such as displaying images during biographical work or group gymnastics, they fostered social interaction and indirect conversation, as well as group identity building. However, they were firmly excluded from roles requiring emotional depth or relational care, which seems to be a tension between the imagination of designers and policy makers and the expectations of caregivers². Therefore, one caregiver explained the importance of maintaining a balance between technological integration and human presence:

“And that can be the limit, because sometimes individuality can get lost in the daily grind. But that is our task and our challenge for the future, to ensure that this is the norm in care. (...) When do you say what about data protection? Or how to deal with it? Then I don’t think it’s a big problem. It’s more about how you deal with it, how you implement it, how you integrate it. So that you don’t feel like there are just robots running around and they can’t really talk to anybody. So, the social aspect must continue.” (Dorn)

Caregivers consistently established ethical boundaries. They did this in situations that required responsibility, empathy, or direct human involvement. This could include administering medication or assisting with personal hygiene. Such scenarios are not currently feasible with existing robotic systems, highlighting the discrepancy between caregivers’ ethical concerns and the actual capabilities of present-day SARs:

“But I always think that wherever responsibility or human affection is involved, I think that robotics simply cannot and should not, in my opinion, replace humans. So, when it comes to giving pills or food or going to the toilet or things like that, I think a robot has no place there.” (Pieper)

This boundary setting underscores the belief that while SARs can play a supportive role, they must not compromise with the relational and ethical core of caregiving. However, caregivers recognized that these boundaries are not fixed. However, end-of-life care emerged as an ethical boundary seemingly non-negotiable:

“I would never use [a robot] in a palliative setting. It’s a time when you need human closeness. A dying person or someone in palliative care needs so much care and attention that no robot can provide. Palliative care and end-of-life care, I always do myself.” (Erich)

Another caregiver expressed similar sentiments, but acknowledged potential future challenges that might make a shift in attitudes necessary:

“In the last phase of life, like end-of-life care, there is so much empathy needed. I think if there’s ever a situation where we don’t have enough staff, maybe a robot would be better than nothing. But for now, these moments require a human presence.” (Mehl)

The quotes show that caregivers negotiate the ethical boundaries of SAR use. While SARs were welcomed for certain routine and logistical tasks, caregivers maintained firm limits regarding relational and emotional aspects of care, particularly in palliative and end-of-life settings. However,

²An exception might be Paro, which is used in physical-affective interactions (e.g. reassurance through touch or basal stimulation through vibration) and is positively evaluated by the interviewees. However, the new generation of SARs focuses more on social-communicative aspects (e.g. with generative AI^[35]), which are viewed more critically by the caregivers interviewed.

their awareness of future challenges suggests that ethical boundaries are not static but require ongoing dialogue as both the challenges and the role of technology in care continue to evolve. In the reflective phase, professionals critically evaluated the triad. They sought to ethically allocate professional responsibilities and maintain relational integrity.

4 Discussion

Our study contributes to current debates on the SAR integration in elderly care by showing how care relationships are shifting from a dyadic to a triadic model. This shift does not follow a linear technological logic but emerges through a dynamic interplay between the affordances of SARs and the interpretive practices of caregivers. Initially, caregivers often exhibit reluctance towards SARs based on a dyadic understanding of care, fearing the replacement of relational dimensions by technology. However, through practical engagement, these assumptions are recalibrated. Our findings show that SARs provide certain social affordances – opportunities for engagement, stimulation or comfort – but these affordances are not automatically realized. Instead, caregivers selectively take up or resist them, depending on their professional values, experiences and ethical considerations^[36]. This highlights the mediated role of technology in care, where meaning and practice emerge through use^[28]. The emerging triadic model of care reflects not only a functional response to technological limitations, but also a normative negotiation of what constitutes ‘good care’. Our study confirms concerns that SARs introduce new responsibilities for caregivers, potentially increasing their workload^[27]. Caregivers must address technical challenges, adapt their interactions with the robot, and ensure that SAR practices adhere to professional standards. These findings align with observations that users often adjust their behavior to align with the robot’s capabilities^[7]. These observations raise questions about the implications for user autonomy and the extent to which SARs influence caregiving practices. Caregivers maintain a strong sense of responsibility for preserving the relational and moral integrity of care. They actively mediate human-robot interactions, redirecting them in a way that supports, rather than replaces, the human-centered essence of care. Their actions demonstrate that SAR integration is never purely technological; rather, it is shaped by how professionals understand the technology in relation to their ethical and professional values. Thus, the triadic model is not a passive outcome, but rather a situated and reflexive achievement. This highlights tensions embedded in SAR affordances: while they are designed to support care, they inevitably create new demands and expectations. Caregivers resist some of these demands, e.g., by restricting robots to routine tasks. They establish boundaries that are not solely dictated by technical capacity but rather reflect a broader professional ethos. This selective acceptance raises important questions for care policy and design: should future SARs be built to afford only what professionals are willing to accept? Or should they more deliberately challenge existing care practices? As demonstrated by our study and others^[37, 38], the successful implementation of SARs depends on involving care professionals. However, we argue that the caregivers’ self-understanding is reconfigured as they interact with SARs. This process of negotiation and boundary setting is central to how ethical frameworks are enacted in practice. Finally, our findings highlight a shift in professional identity. Caregivers increasingly see their role not only as maintaining good relationships with recipients, but also as curating meaningful human-technology interactions. They are becoming ‘bridge builders’ – mediating between technological innovation and the emotional, ethical and practical needs of elderly care. To fulfill this role, caregivers need ongoing support, reflection and professional development to ensure that technological integration enhances rather than undermines the human essence of care. Our study has the following limitations: 1) a small sample size and potential bias arising from the self-selecting processes of institutions and caregivers; 2) the cross-sectional nature of the study, whereby caregivers’ experiences were interpreted retrospectively; 3) not including the perspective of care recipients. Nevertheless, our findings are consistent with broader empirical research, while illuminating gaps in the existing literature. Our study takes a retrospective approach on SAR integration and changes of the caregivers’ relationship model.

5 Conclusion

The SAR implementation into elderly care can challenge professionals' understanding of 'good care' as well as their self-understanding. As empirically shown, caregivers' perspectives are changing from a dyadic to a triadic model where they act as bridge builders between technology and relational care. While SARs support practical tasks and social engagement, caregivers do not see them as replacing the emotional depth, adaptability, and moral agency that are central to human caregiving. Our findings show that caregivers actively mediate SARs interactions to ensure that they enhance rather than diminish relational care. Caregivers emphasize that SARs should complement, not replace, their work, thus preserving the human-centered nature of caregiving. This highlights the need for structured training and participatory implementation to empower caregivers to integrate SARs effectively. Ultimately, the success of SARs depends on their recognition as supportive tools rather than substitutes for human care. The bridge-builder metaphor encapsulates how caregivers navigate technological change to ensure that relational care remains at the heart of elder support. As care becomes increasingly technologized, maintaining this balance is critical for both care recipients and caregivers' professional identities.

6 Statements and Declarations

Author contributions

MB, CK, JH and RR conceived the original idea for the article. MB and CK conducted the interviews, and MB, CK and CVK analyzed the data. MB drafted the initial manuscript, with all authors contributing to revising and refining subsequent versions. All authors have approved the final version of the manuscript. CK, RR, and JH supervised the project and are the principal investigators. RR and CK secured funding for the project.

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Conflict of Interest

None declared.

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Interview guide

Table 1: Interview guide (Part 1)

Main questions	Possible inquiries	Specific questions	
1) We have already said that the focus of the interview is on the use of social robotics...	What does the robot do? How does the robot do this? When is the robot used? How often? With whom? Who uses it?	How would you describe the robot to someone unfamiliar?	Non verbal
2) Can you give me a typical example of a situation where the robot is used?	Who is present? Your role? What does the robot do? How does the resident interact? How would it look without the robot?	What would you have done without the robot?	Non verbal Can you describe ...? How did the resident react?
3) How do you experience using the robot?	What changes with use? Advantages? Challenges? Your role? Feelings? Changes over time?	Any advice for others without experience?	Non verbal How do you deal with it? Can you describe ...?
4) What do you think – how do residents experience the robot?	How do you perceive residents? Reactions to the robot? Changes from regular use? Impact on relationships?	How do you introduce the robot? What do relatives think?	Non verbal Can you describe more? What do you attribute this to?

Table 2: Interview guide (Part 2)

Main questions	Possible inquiries	Specific questions	
5) Do you remember the robot's introduction?	How long used? How introduced? How did you feel? How did others react?	How have things changed?	Non verbal Example? What happened?
5a) Alternative start: How was your first experience with the robot?	How introduced to the robot? Initial feelings? First impressions of residents/colleagues?	How have things changed since then?	Non verbal Example? What happened?
6) How do you evaluate the future of robotics in care?	Hopes for future use? Concerns? Where do you see limits?	What do you think? Do you see that?	Non verbal
In conclusion: Is there anything else important to you about the use of the robot in daily care that we haven't discussed?			

References

- [1] Pols, J. *Care at a Distance. On the Closeness of Technology* (Amsterdam University Press, Amsterdam, 2012). URL <https://doi.org/10.1515/9789048513017>.
- [2] Coeckelbergh, M. Artificial agents, good care, and modernity. *Theoretical Medicine and Bioethics* **36** (4), 265–277 (2015). URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s11017-015-9331-y>. doi: 10.1007/s11017-015-9331-y .
- [3] Friesacher, H. Pflege und Technik—eine kritische Analyse. *Pflege & Gesellschaft* **15** (4), 293–313 (2010) .
- [4] Sandelowski, M. *Devices & desires: gender, technology, and American nursing Studies in social medicine* (Univ. of North Carolina Press, Chapel Hill, 2005).
- [5] Matarić, M. J. & Scassellati, B. in *Socially Assistive Robotics* (eds Siciliano, B. & Khatib, O.) *Springer Handbook of Robotics 1973–1994* (Springer, Cham, 2016). URL https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-319-32552-1_73. Series Title: Springer Handbooks.
- [6] Vandemeulebroucke, T., de Casterlé, B. D. & Gastmans, C. Ethics of socially assistive robots in aged-care settings: A socio-historical contextualisation. *J Med Ethics* **46** (2), 128–136 (2020). doi: 10.1136/medethics-2019-105615, number: 2 .
- [7] Abdi, J., Al-Hindawi, A., Ng, T. & Vizcaychipi, M. P. Scoping review on the use of socially assistive robot technology in elderly care. *BMJ Open* **8** (2), e018815 (2018). URL <https://bmjopen.bmj.com/lookup/doi/10.1136/bmjopen-2017-018815>. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2017-018815 .
- [8] International Council of Nurses. The icn code of ethics for nurses. Tech. Rep., ICN, Geneva (2021). URL https://www.icn.ch/sites/default/files/2023-06/ICN_Code-of-Ethics_EN_Web.pdf. ISBN 978-92-95099-94-4, Accessed 12 May 2025.
- [9] Deutscher Ethikrat. *Robotik für gute Pflege: Stellungnahme: 10. März 2020* (Deutscher Ethikrat, Berlin, 2020).
- [10] Fisher, B. & Tronto, J. C. in *Toward a feminist theory of caring* (eds Abel, E. K. & Nelson, M. K.) *Circles of care: Work and identity in women's lives* 35–62 (SUNY Press, Albany, 1990).
- [11] Zölllick, J. C. et al. in *Akzeptanz von Technikeinsatz in der Pflege: Zwischenergebnisse einer Befragung unter professionell Pflegenden* (eds Jacobs, K., Kuhlmeier, A., Greß, S., Klauber, J. & Schwinger, A.) *Pflege-Report 2019* 211–218 (Springer, Berlin, 2020). URL http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-662-58935-9_17.
- [12] Zölllick, J., Kuhlmeier, A., Nordheim, J. & Blüher, S. Robotik in der Pflege – Potenziale und Grenzen. *Der Hautarzt* **73** (5), 405–407 (2022). URL <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00105-022-04965-y>. doi: 10.1007/s00105-022-04965-y .
- [13] Hülsken-Giesler, M. & Remmers, H. *Robotische Systeme für die Pflege: Potenziale und Grenzen autonomer Assistenzsysteme aus pflegewissenschaftlicher Sicht* No. Band 17 in *Pflegewissenschaft und Pflegebildung* (V&R unipress, Göttingen, 2020).
- [14] Vandemeulebroucke, T., Dierckx De Casterlé, B. & Gastmans, C. The use of care robots in aged care: A systematic review of argument-based ethics literature. *Archives of Gerontology and Geriatrics* **74**, 15–25 (2018). URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0167494317302790>. doi: 10.1016/j.archger.2017.08.014 .
- [15] Vandemeulebroucke, T., de Casterlé, B. D. & Gastmans, C. Socially assistive robots in aged care: Ethical orientations beyond the care-romantic and technology-deterministic Gaze. *Sci Eng Ethics* **27** (2), 1–20 (2021). doi: 10.1007/s11948-021-00296-8, number: 2 .
- [16] Yuan, S., Coghlan, S., Lederman, R. & Waycott, J. Ethical design of social robots in aged care: A literature review using an ethics of care perspective. *International Journal of Social Robotics* **15** (9-10), 1637–1654 (2023). URL <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s12369-023-01053-6>. doi: 10.1007/s12369-023-01053-6 .
- [17] Sparrow, R. & Sparrow, L. In the hands of machines? The future of aged care. *Minds & Machines* **16** (2), 141–161 (2006). URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s11023-006-9030-6>. doi: 10.1007/s11023-006-9030-6 .
- [18] Sharkey, A. & Sharkey, N. Granny and the robots: ethical issues in robot care for the elderly. *Ethics Inf Technol* **14** (1), 27–40 (2012). URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10676-010-9234-6>. doi: 10.1007/s10676-010-9234-6 .
- [19] Sparrow, R. Robots in aged care: a dystopian future? *AI & SOCIETY* **31** (4), 445–454 (2016).

- URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00146-015-0625-4>. doi: 10.1007/s00146-015-0625-4 .
- [20] Decker, M. Caregiving robots and ethical reflection: the perspective of interdisciplinary technology assessment. *AI & SOCIETY* **22** (3), 315–330 (2007). doi: 10.1007/s00146-007-0151-0 .
- [21] Parks, J. A. Lifting the Burden of Women’s Care Work: Should Robots Replace the “Human Touch”? *Hypatia* **25** (1), 100–120 (2010). URL https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/S088753670002434X/type/journal_article. doi: 10.1111/j.1527-2001.2009.01086.x .
- [22] Feil-Seifer, D. & Matarić, M. Socially Assistive Robotics. *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine* **18** (1), 24–31 (2011). doi: 10.1109/MRA.2010.940150 .
- [23] Ienca, M., Jotterand, F., Vică, C. & Elger, B. Social and Assistive Robotics in Dementia Care: Ethical Recommendations for Research and Practice. *International Journal of Social Robotics* **8** (4), 565–573 (2016). URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s12369-016-0366-7>. doi: 10.1007/s12369-016-0366-7 .
- [24] Moyle, W. *et al.* Using a therapeutic companion robot for dementia symptoms in long-term care: reflections from a cluster-RCT. *Aging & Mental Health* **23** (3), 329–336 (2019). URL <https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=cin20&AN=135909143&site=ehost-live>. doi: 10.1080/13607863.2017.1421617, place: Oxfordshire, Publisher: Routledge .
- [25] Körtner, T. Ethical challenges in the use of social service robots for elderly people. *Zeitschrift für Gerontologie und Geriatrie* **49** (4), 303–307 (2016). URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00391-016-1066-5>. doi: 10.1007/s00391-016-1066-5 .
- [26] Preuß, D. & Legal, F. Living with the animals: animal or robotic companions for the elderly in smart homes? *Journal of medical ethics* **43** (6), 407–410 (2017). doi: 10.1136/medethics-2016-103603, place: England .
- [27] Martani, A., Tian, Y. J. A., Felber, N. & Wangmo, T. Gerontechnologies, ethics, and care phases: Secondary analysis of qualitative interviews. *Nurs Ethics* **31** (1), 141–155 (2024). URL <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/09697330241238340>. doi: 10.1177/09697330241238340 .
- [28] Verbeek, P.-P. in *Toward a Theory of Technological Mediation: A Program for Postphenomenological Research* (eds Friis, J.-K. B. O. & Crease, R. P.) *Technoscience and postphenomenology: the Manhattan papers* 189–204 (Lexington Books, Lanham, 2015).
- [29] Hülsken-Giesler, M. & Daxberger, S. in *Robotik in der Pflege aus pflegewissenschaftlicher Perspektive* (ed. Bendel, O.) *Pflegeroboter* 125–139 (Springer, Wiesbaden, 2018). URL http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-658-22698-5_7.
- [30] Zölllick, J., Rössle, S., Kluy, L., Kuhlmeier, A. & Blüher, S. Potenziale und Herausforderungen von sozialen Robotern für Beziehungen älterer Menschen: eine Bestandsaufnahme mittels rapid review“. *Z Gerontol Geriatr* **55** (4), 298–304 (2022). URL <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00391-021-01932-5>. doi: 10.1007/s00391-021-01932-5, number: 4 .
- [31] Charmaz, K. *Constructing Grounded Theory* 2 edn (SAGE Publications Ltd, London/Thousand Oaks, 2014).
- [32] Helfferich, C. *Die Qualität qualitativer Daten: Manual zur Durchführung qualitativer Interviews* 3. edn (VS Verlag, Wiesbaden, 2009).
- [33] Bubeck, M., Haltaufderheide, J., Sakowsky, R. & Ranisch, R. *Erklärung Potsdamer Bürgerinnen und Bürger zur Robotik in der Altenpflege* (Fakultät für Gesundheitswissenschaften Brandenburg, Universität Potsdam, 2024).
- [34] Tong, A., Sainsbury, P. & Craig, J. Consolidated criteria for reporting qualitative research (COREQ): a 32-item checklist for interviews and focus groups. *International Journal for Quality in Health Care* **19** (6), 349–357 (2007). URL <https://doi.org/10.1093/intqhc/mzm042>. doi: 10.1093/intqhc/mzm042 .
- [35] Ranisch, R. & Haltaufderheide, J. Rapid Integration of LLMs in Healthcare Raises Ethical Concerns: An Investigation into Deceptive Patterns in Social Robots. *Digital Society* **4** (1), 7 (2025). URL <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s44206-025-00161-2>. doi: 10.1007/s44206-025-00161-2 .
- [36] Pfadenhauer, M. & Dukat, C. Professionalisierung lebensweltlicher Krisen durch Technik?: Zur Betreuung demenziell erkrankter Personen mittels sozial assistiver Robotik. *Österreichische*

- Zeitschrift für Soziologie* **41** (S1), 115–131 (2016). URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s11614-016-0210-1>. doi: 10.1007/s11614-016-0210-1 .
- [37] Klebbe, R., Klüber, K., Dahms, R. & Onnasch, L. Caregivers’ Perspectives on Human–Robot Collaboration in Inpatient Elderly Care Settings. *Machines* **11** (1), 1–26 (2023). doi: 10.3390/machines11010034, number: 1 .
- [38] Nielsen, S. *et al.* Implementing ethical aspects in the development of a robotic system for nursing care: a qualitative approach. *BMC nursing* **21** (1), 180 (2022). doi: 10.1186/s12912-022-00959-2, place: England .